

Synthesis of 2-Methyl-2-(*m*-methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexanone

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Synthesis of 2-methyl-2-(*m*-methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexanone, an important intermediate towards the synthesis of resin acids has been described.

DITERPENOIDS have been known for over a century and their chemistry has come under extensive study during the past fifty years. But syntheses of these compounds have been mainly confined to the last three decades. Much of the interest in their syntheses stems from their resemblance, especially in the A and B rings, provides for a comparison of the methods used in the synthesis of the two systems.

2-Methyl-2-(*m*-methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexanone serves as an important intermediate towards resin acid syntheses. It is prepared by Grignard reaction between *m*-bromoanisole and cyclohexanone to yield 1-(*m*-methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexanol, which on dehydration using oxalic acid in toluene yielded 1-(*m*-methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexene. The cyclohexene was

converted into the corresponding nitrosochloride following Ginsberg's method¹. This was later treated with pyridine, followed by dilution with ether and extracted with Claisen alkali. The alkaline solution on acidification yielded 2-(*m*-methoxyphenyl)-cyclohex-2-enone oxime. The unsaturated ketone was regenerated from the oxime and was reduced catalytically to give 2-(*m*-methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexanone. This was subsequently methylated using methyl iodide in the presence of sodamide to yield 2-methyl-2-(*m*-methoxyphenyl)-cyclohexanone. Thus A and C rings of the resin acid are synthesised.

References

1. D. GINSBERG and R. PAPP, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 516.